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Research Article

**INVESTIGATION THE FREQUENCY OF PATIENTS
PRESENTED WITH RETINAL DETACHMENT IN DIFFERENT
AGE GROUPS AT OPD OF OPHTHALMOLOGY
DEPARTMENT OF HOLY FAMILY HOSPITAL, RAWALPINDI****¹Dr Fatima Muzammil, ²Dr. Naeem Fatima, ³Dr Sara Akram****¹Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi, ²Allied Hospital Faisalabad, ³Sharif Medical and Dental
College Lahore.****Abstract:**

The objective of my study was to find out the frequency of patients presented with retinal detachment in different age groups at ophthalmology department of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi. A descriptive study was planned involving 40 patients of retinal detachment visited eye opd of ophthalmology department of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi during 15 August 2018 to 15 Dec 2018. Patients were exposed to various diagnostic procedures to confirm RD and its severity. These diagnostic procedures include detailed fundus examination with slit lamp, ophthalmoscope (direct and indirect), ultrasonography (B-scan), Goldmann three mirrors and fundus camera. According to severity, management was decided. Proper management and visual prognosis were explained to patients.

Keywords: *Retinal detachment (RD), Proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR), Proliferative vitreoretinopathy (PVR), Posterior vitreous detachment(PVD), Pseudophakia, Trauma, Myopic Degeneration.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Retinal detachment is the term used to describe detachment of the neurosensory retina from the underlying membrane, the retinal pigment epithelium. The separation of the two layers takes place within the fissure formed by the invagination of the optic cup. The annual incidence of RRD is 10 to 15 per 100,000 persons. Multiple studies have shown that males are more frequently affected than females by a ratio of 1.3 - 1.5 to 1. Racial differences have also been described. Asian population was found to have an increased incidence of RRD, due to a higher prevalence of myopia. Risk factors for RRD include retinal breaks, lattice degeneration, myopia, cataract surgery, trauma, and a history of RRD in the other eye. Combinations of these factors in a single eye increase the risk of RRD. The risk of RRD increases with the increase of axial length. Low myopes (1 to 3 diopters) have a 4-fold risk and higher myopes (>3 diopters) have a 10-fold risk compared with that of emmetropes. The overall risk of RRD after cataract surgery is approximately 1%. Vitreous loss, increased axial length, lattice degeneration, Nd:YAG laser capsulotomy, Caucasian race, and younger age have been reported to increase the risk of RRD after cataract surgery. Two large studies found that the risk of RRD after cataract surgery is 6 to 7 times greater than that of phakic control groups. Blunt or penetrating ocular injuries cause changes in the structure of the vitreous or retina and increase risk of RRD. The risk of RRD by blunt trauma in younger age group is decreasing because of a formed (not liquefied) vitreous. The detachment may not be symptomatic for years even though nearly all breaks caused by a blunt trauma may occur at the time of the injury.

METHODOLOGY:

Descriptive hospital-based study at Holy Family hospital, Rawalpindi in which patients having retinal detachment with pseudophakia and post traumatic history with or without proliferative vitreoretinopathy (PVR) posterior vitreous detachment (PVD) and

proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) were included. Sampling technique was consecutive sampling. The data of the patients exposed to diagnostic criteria of retinal detachment recorded on especially designed proforma. Data collection tools and procedures were visual acuity charts (Snellen chart), pinhole vision, Tonometry for intraocular pressure measurement, Slit-lamp examination with non contact lens, Fundoscopy of dilated eyes by Direct and Indirect ophthalmoscope to find retinal breaks and detached areas of retina, Perimetry (visual field test), Ultrasonography (B-scan), OCT (optical coherence topography), Goldmann three mirrors gives visibility of whole interior of eye including the angle of anterior chamber, Panfunduscope lens (90D) for panretinal photocoagulation (PRP) and Retinoscopy by retinoscope in case of high myopia, aphakia and pseudophakia

RESULTS:

Results are drawn on the basis of selected variables i.e gender, age, type of retinal detachment, unilateral/bilateral, association of RD with different conditions (PDR, PVR, Trauma, myopic degeneration) and diagnostic technique. A sample of 40 patients studied in hospital based study. Among 40 patients 22 were males and 18 were females. According to age groups 0-20yr (15%), 21-40yr (5%), 41-60yr (47.5%), 61-80yr (32.5%) were presented with retinal detachment. According to types of retinal detachment, patients with rhegmatogenous RD (25%), traumatic RD (12.5%), tractional RD (37.5%) and total RD (25%) were presented in eye opd. According to laterality, 90% patients were presented with unilateral presentation, 10% patients were presented with bilateral presentation. According to associations of RD with different conditions, RD with PDR (52.5%), RD with PVR (30%), RD with myopic degeneration (2.5%) and RD with trauma (15%). According to diagnostic procedure, 58% patients by 90D lens and 42% patients by B-scan were diagnosed.

Table 1. showing Gender wise distribution

Gender	No. of Patients	Percentage%
Male	22	55%
Female	18	45%
Total	40	100%

Table 2. showing age wise distribution

Age	No. of Patients	Percentage%
0-20yr	6	15%
21-40yr	2	5%
41-60yr	19	47.5%
61-80yr	13	32.5%

Table 3. showing RD associated with PDR, PVR, Trauma & Myopic Degeneration

RD with different Conditions	No. Of Patients	Percentage%
PVR	12	30%
PDR	21	52.50%
Myopic Degeneration	1	2.50%
Trauma	6	15%
Total	40	100%

Table 4. Showing unilateral and bilateral RD patients

Unilateral/ involvement	Bilateral	No. Of Patients	Percentage%
Unilateral		36	90%
Bilateral		4	10%
Total		40	100%

Table.5 showing type wise distribution of retinal detachment

Type of Retinal Detachment	No. of Patients	Percentage
Rhegmatogenous RD	10	25%
Traumatic RD	5	12.5%
Tractional RD	15	37.5%
Total RD	10	25%
Total	40	100%

Table .6 showing frequency of patients exposed to different procedures for diagnosis

Diagnostic procedures	No. Of Patients	Percentage%
90D lens	23	90%
B-scan	17	10%
Total	40	100%

DISCUSSION:

This study was designed to find out the frequency of retinal detachment in different age groups. It was a hospital based study. Population based study was not possible due to limited resources and time period .All types of retinal detachment (traumatic,tractional,rhegmatogenous,exudative) are vision threatening. The purpose of my study was to minimize the visual loss by diagnosing the patients at

early stage of the disease, providing prompt management according to severity of RD and by controlling predisposing factors(diabetes,trauma) that are responsible for RD..After the detailed diagnoses, the patients were referred to the ophthalmologist for treatment and advised to follow the instructions of the doctor and come on follow ups regularly so as to control the further damage.

CONCLUSION:

Retinal detachment is a sight threatening disease. Early diagnosis, proper management and guarded visual prognosis are mandatory to prevent visual loss. From this study, it is concluded that males are more affected with RD than females. RD is more common in 4th to 6th decade of life. Regarding to types, tractional RD is more common. Unilateral presentation is more common. RD with PDR is more commonly associated than other conditions. More commonly examination and diagnosis is carried out by 90D lens.

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